

**EFFECT OF TWO DIFFERENT ANTI-INFLAMMATORY DRUGS IN
POLYPRAGMASIA ON THE MORPHOMETRIC PARAMETERS OF THE NON-
WHITE RATS ESOPHAGUS IN NORMAL STATUS AND POLYPRAGMASIA**

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6536577>

Temirov Orifjon Olimovich

*Republican Specialized Scientific-Practical
Medical Center of Oncology*

The desire to increase the effectiveness of treatment in the body of patients, to help the patient get rid of all the diseases that have developed in him, inevitably leads to the appointment of many drugs (medications) - which in turn leads to polypragmasia in the patient. Polypragmasia is a serious problem of the health care system, as it is clinically manifested by a decrease in the effectiveness of pharmacotherapy and the development of unwanted adverse reactions, as well as a significant increase in health care costs.

The term “polypragmasia” is often used in the medical literature, but there is no generally accepted definition.

For this purpose, the parameters of comparison of morphometric parameters of the esophagus of white non-white rats in the normal state and in the case of the effect of anti-inflammatory drugs in polypragmasia were studied. The aim of the study was to supplement the data on morphological and morphometric parameters in esophageal tissue.

Materials and methods.

Based on macroscopic and microscopic studies of esophageal tissue during the examination, a total of 40 esophageal tissues divided into two groups were pathohistologically examined. For general morphology, 1.5x1.5 cm pieces were cut from the esophagus and solidified in 10% neutralized formalin. After washing for 2–4 h in running water, it was dehydrated in increased concentrations of alcohols and xylene, then paraffin was poured and the blocks were prepared. Incisions of 5–8 µm were made from paraffin blocks and stained with hematoxylin and eosin. The following anti-inflammatory agents were used to study the effect of polypragmasia in experimental groups of white non-white rats in the experimental group:

Aspirin (derivatives of NYaQD-salicylic acid), paracetamol (derivatives of NYaQD-anilides).

Conclusions and conclusions.

The white rats obtained for the experiment were divided into 2 groups (n = 40): I – group - (intact) control (n = 20); Group II - white rats receiving 2 types of nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, paracetamol 15 mg / kg, aspirin 5 mg / kg (n = 20); Doses of this drug were calculated empirically and administered in the form of a solution into the stomach every day for 10 days.

From 141 to 150 days of development, white non-white rats in the Control Group were injected with 0.5 ml of distilled water into the stomach through a metal probe for 10 days.

Incisions taken from the esophagus of white-bred rats were morphometrically examined and the size of esophageal tissue cells was measured using an ocular micrometer, in which we used a trinocular microscope manufactured in China. DN-107t / Model NLCD-307b (Roman, China).

Thus, the use of a set of nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), as described above, led to the appearance of the following pathomorphological changes in the esophagus in rats: hyperemia of the mucous membrane in the examined esophageal tissue, tumors, areas of epithelial destruction.

LITERATURE

1. V.N.Karkishchenko, N.N.Karkishchenko, E.B.Shustov Farmakologicheskie osnovy terapii // Rukovodstvo dlya vrachey i studentov. Moscow, St. Petersburg 2018

2. Golovanova E.V. Zashchita slizistoy obolochki JKT ot povrejdayushchego deystviya nesteroidnyx protivovospalitelnyx preparations // Klinicheskaya gerontologiya. - 2017. - №1-2. - S.47-51.

3. Dikareva E.A., Pimanov S.I., Makarenko E.V. Otsenka riska razvitiya gastropatii, indutsirovannoy priyomom nesteroidnyx protivovospalitelnyx sredstv, na osnove mezhdunarodnyx soglasitelnyx dokumentov // Vestnik VGMU. - 2015. - №5. - S.39-45.

4. Dubikov A.I. Nesteroidnye protivovospalitelnye preparations: eshche raz o glavnom // Klinicheskaya gerontologiya. -2009. - -137-13.

5. Efimov A.L., Sigua B.V., Filaretova L.P. Acute ulcers and erosions of the gastrointestinal tract, induced by nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs: etiology, pathogenesis, treatment tactics // Vestnik Rossiyskoy Voenno-meditsinskoy akademii. - 2017. - № 1 (57). - S. 198-204.

6. Karateev A.E., Nasonov E.L., Yaxno N.N., Ivashkin V.T., Chichasova N.V., Alekseeva L.I and others. Rational application of nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory

drugs (NPVP) in clinical practice // Clinical recommendations. Modern rheumatology. №1. 2015. S.4-18

7. Paxomova I.G., Belousova L.N. Inflammation of the upper gastrointestinal tract, associated with the reception of nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs // Effective pharmacotherapy. - 2014. - № 49. - p. 24-31.

8. Karateev A.E., Yaxno N.N., Lazebnik L.B. and dr. Application of nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs. Clinical recommendations. M. : IMA-press, 2009.

9. Hawkey C.J., Lain L., Harper S.E. et al. Influence of risk factors on endoscopic and clinical ulcers in patients taking rofecoxib or ibuprofen in two randomized controlled trials // Aliment. Pharmacol. Ther. 2001. Vol. 15. № 10. P. 1593–1601.

10. Karateev A.E., Yaxno N.N., Lazebnik L.B. and dr. Application of nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs. Clinical recommendations. M. : IMA-press, 2009.

11. Venerino M., Malfertheiner P. Interaction of Helicobacter pylori infection and nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs in gastric and duodenal ulcers // Helicobacter. 2010. Vol. 15. № 4. P. 239–250.

12. Papatheodoridis G.V., Sougioultzis S., Archimandritis A.J. Effects of Helicobacter pylori and nonsteroidal antiinflammatory drugs on peptic ulcer disease: a systematic review // Clin. Gastroenterol. Hepatol. 2006. Vol. 4. № 2. P. 130–142.

13. Malfertheiner P., Megraud F., O'Morain C.A. et al. Management of Helicobacter pylori infection - the Maastricht IV / Florence Consensus Report // Gut. 2012. Vol. 61. № 5. P. 646–664.

14. Bigard M., Pelletier A. Esophageal complications of non steroidal antiinflammatory drug // Gastroenterol. Clin. Biol. 2004. Spec. № 3. P. 58–61.

15. Karateev A.E., Uspenskiy Yu.P., Paxomova I.G. and dr. With NPVP and pathology of the esophagus: associated with the main symptoms of gastroesophageal reflux disease, the frequency of development and risk factors for erosive esophagitis // Experimental and clinical gastroenterology. 2008. № 3. S. 6–11.

16. Ruszniewski P., Soufflet C., Barthélémy P. Nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drug use as a risk factor for gastroesophageal reflux disease: an observational study // Aliment. Pharmacol. Ther. 2008. Vol. 28. № 9. P. 1134–1139.

17. Pakhomova I.G., Uspenskiy Yu.P., Edemskaya M.A. and dr. Porazheniya pishchevoda u bolnyx osteoarthritis, prinyimayushchix nesteroidnye

protivovospalitelnye preparations // Prakticheskaya meditsina. 2012. № 3. S. 86–90.

18. Karateev A.E., Barskova V.G. Novoe v dokazatelnoy meditsine. Safety nimesulida: emotsii or vzveshennaya otsenka? // Consilium Medicum. 2007. № 2. S. 34–37.

19. Taha A., Angerson W., Morran C. Correlation between erosive oesophageal and gastro-duodenal diseases. The influence of aspirin, simple analgesics, and Helicobacter pylori // Eur. J. Gastroenterol. Hepatol. 2002. Vol. 14. № 12. P. 1313–1317.

20. Avidan B., Sonnenberg A., Schnell T. et al. Risk factors for erosive reflux esophagitis: a case-control study // Am. J. Gastroenterol. 2001. Vol. 96. № 1. P. 41–46.

21. Vane J.R. The fight against rheumatism: from willow bark to COX-1 sparing drug // J. Physiol. Pharmacol. 2000. Vol. 5. № 4. Pt. 1. P. 573–586.

22. Tsvetkova E.S. Effectiveness and tolerability of stupenchatoy therapy Movalisom (meloxicam) in rheumatic diseases // Terapevticheskiy arxiv. 2004. № 12. S. 78–80.

23. Hawkey C., Kahan A., Steinbrick K et al. Gastrointestinal tolerability of meloxicam compared to diclofenac in osteoarthritis patients // Br. J. Rheumatol. 1998. Vol. 37. № 9. P. 937–945.

24. Olimova Aziza Zokirovna, (2021, July). COMPARATIVE CHARACTERISTICS OF THE MORPHOLOGICAL PARAMETERS OF THE LIVER AT DIFFERENT PERIODS OF TRAUMATIC BRAIN INJURY. In Euro-Asia Conferences (pp. 139-142).

25. Olimova Aziza Zokirovna. Частота Встречаемости Миомы Матки У Женщин В Репродуктивном Возрасте. JOURNAL OF ADVANCED RESEARCH AND STABILITY (JARS). Volume: 01 Issue: 06 | 2021. 551-556 p

26. Olimova Aziza Zokirovna, Sanoyev Bakhtiyor Abdurasulovich. OVARIAN DISEASES IN AGE OF REPRODUCTIVE WOMEN: DERMOID CYST. Volume: 01 Issue: 06 | 2021. 154-161 p

27. Olimova Aziza Zokirovna. РЕПРОДУКТИВ ЁШДАГИ ЭРКАКЛАРДА БЕПУШТЛИК САБАБЛАРИ: БУХОРО ТУМАНИ ЭПИДЕМИОЛОГИЯСИ. SCIENTIFIC PROGRESS. 2021 й 499-502p

28. Olimova Aziza Zokirovna .MACRO- AND MICROSCOPIC STRUCTURE OF THE LIVER OF THREE MONTHLY WHITE RATS. ACADEMIC RESEARCH IN EDUCATIONAL SCIENCES /2021 й. 309-312 p

